

Research Article

OceanFlow: Graphic User Interface (GUI) and Intuitive Mobile Application for Scuba Safety in Malaysia

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Abstract: This research presents a comprehensive study on the development of a graphic user interface (GUI) and an intuitive mobile application aimed at enhancing scuba diving safety in Malaysia. The primary focus of this research is the creation of OceanFlow, a mobile application designed to provide real-time notifications of tide changes, thereby improving the safety and decision-making capabilities of scuba divers. Scuba diving presents unique challenges and risks, particularly due to the dynamic nature of underwater environments and the significant impact of tidal changes. Traditional methods of anticipating tide fluctuations are often inadequate for divers, who require timely and accurate information to avoid hazardous conditions. This research identifies the critical need for a specialised tool that can deliver real-time tide forecasts in a user-friendly manner. The study begins with an in-depth review of the literature on scuba diving safety, the impact of tidal changes, and the role of technology in mitigating related risks. The research highlights the gaps in existing tools and applications, emphasising the lack of accessible and intuitive solutions for divers. Following this, the methodology for developing the OceanFlow application is outlined, including the design principles and features essential for an effective GUI tailored to scuba divers. Key features of OceanFlow include personalised dive profiles, real-time dive log monitoring, educational resources, and dive schedule planning. The application's user interface is designed to simplify complex tidal data, making it easily interpretable for divers of all skill levels. The integration of these features aims to enhance the overall user experience and provide divers with the information they need to make informed decisions.

Keywords: mobile application; graphic user interface; user experience

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1. INTRODUCTION

The scuba diving environment is packed with hazards, particularly tide shifts emerging as an additional danger to scuba diver safety. Unlike other water activities where tide forecasting technologies are readily available, scuba divers lack tailored applications to effectively anticipate tide fluctuations. While surfers often turn to tide charts to assess wave conditions, divers rely on anecdotal information or general weather forecasts, leaving them vulnerable to unforeseen threats.

Recent research highlights the dangers caused by unanticipated surge-tide interactions, underlining the critical necessity for readily available tide forecast tools for divers. Despite the obvious concerns, there is still a noticeable lack of user-friendly software designed to notify divers of oncoming tide changes. This absence of accessible tide forecasting tools presents a substantial risk to scuba diver safety, highlighted by firsthand experiences such as that of Mohammad Rudy bin Musnin during a diving expedition at Koh Li Peh, Thailand (Musnin, 2023). Rudy's encounter starkly illustrates the

potentially life-threatening consequences of failing to anticipate tidal shifts, where calm surface conditions belie turbulent currents beneath.

Moreover, statistical analyses of diving-related fatalities reveal a disturbing trend, with drowning emerging as the leading cause of death among scuba divers, closely followed by cardiovascular issues and arterial gas embolisms. Research by Aquila et al. (2017) and Altepe et al. (2017) highlights the pivotal role of tidal changes in contributing to drowning incidents during diving activities. Similarly, DeGorordo et al. (2003) notes a significant correlation between tidal changes and diving injuries, particularly those related to gas behaviour and pressure fluctuations during descent and ascent.

The absence of broadly accessible tide forecasting technologies tailored to the needs of scuba divers highlights a fundamental gap in diver safety measures. Addressing this challenge necessitates innovative research that bridges the gap between tidal dynamics and diver safety, ultimately reducing hazards and creating a safer diving environment for divers worldwide. Through this study, the researcher aims to contribute to this main objective by identifying the key challenges and evaluating the design principles necessary for developing user-friendly and intuitive tide forecasting tools for scuba divers.

Recent years have seen remarkable progress in tide forecasting technology, with notable strides in forecast models, data assimilation methods, and artificial intelligence integration. These advancements have profoundly impacted oceanographic predictions, offering significant promise for improved forecasting accuracy and disaster preparedness. Scholarly work by Li et al. (2018) underscores the role of artificial neural networks in enhancing ocean tide forecasting, highlighting their contribution to improved prediction accuracy. Similarly, Yadidya (2024) explores the potential of forecast models in global internal tide mapping, indicating their importance in refining oceanographic predictions.

Moreover, studies by Zijl et al. (2015) emphasise the critical role of data assimilation techniques in preventing errors in meteorological forcing from affecting tide-surge model forecasts. By integrating observational data into forecast models, these techniques enhance the reliability of tide predictions, contributing to better coastal management practices. The proposal of advanced models, such as the Physics-Informed Red Tide Deep Learning Forecast Model by Mu et al. (2023), further illustrates the ongoing efforts to incorporate causal-inferred predictors for capturing complex ocean-atmosphere-biology interactions during red tide events. These models hold promise for more nuanced and accurate tide forecasting, particularly in scenarios involving extreme events and high tides.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

In this study, the research methodology will be carefully designed to explore the development of OceanFlow, a mobile application designed to enhance scuba diving safety through real-time tide forecasting and an intuitive user interface (UI).

According to Crouch et al. (2012) in "Doing Research in Design," they argue that design plays a significant role in promoting social change. To understand the societal impact and implications of UI design for water sports applications, a qualitative methods approach will be employed, allowing for a comprehensive exploration of the challenges and opportunities in developing OceanFlow.

The participants for this study will be selected based on their significant involvement and expertise in scuba diving. The primary participants include two PADI Certified scuba instructors, who are also key stakeholders at Tiongman Scuba Dive and Lodge in Kampung Juara, Pulau Tioman. These

interviews aim to gather valuable insights into the practical application of OceanFlow in real-world diving scenarios and to understand the design principles essential for creating an effective and intuitive user interface.

Semi-structured interviews will be conducted with key stakeholders, two PADI Certified scuba instructors from Tiongman Scuba Dive and Lodge in Kampung Juara, Pulau Tioman. The interviews will focus on the following aspects:

1. Experiences with tide changes and their impact on diving safety.
2. Perceptions of existing tide forecasting tools.
3. Expectations and suggestions for the OceanFlow application.

The interviews will be conducted either in person or remotely, depending on the participants' availability and preferences. The responses will be recorded and transcribed for detailed analysis.

3. FINDINGS

3.1 Findings from the Interview

During the interviews, the two PADI Certified scuba instructors provided valuable feedback on their experiences with existing tidal forecasting apps and their expectations from such tools. The insights gathered can be categorised into 5 main areas: tide changes on diving safety, current application usage, desired features, user interface preferences, challenges faced, and overall satisfaction.

1. **Impact of Tide Changes on Diving Safety:** Both instructors emphasised that tidal changes have a significant impact on diving safety. They highlighted how shifts in tides can alter underwater currents and visibility, which are crucial factors affecting diver safety. Accurate predictions of tide movements are therefore essential for planning dives safely and effectively navigating underwater environments.
2. **Current App Usage:** The divers primarily used apps such as Tide Charts, My Tide Times, and Fishing Points for their tidal forecasting needs. They appreciated the basic functionality these apps offered, particularly the real-time updates and tide tables. However, they often found themselves switching between multiple apps to gather all the necessary information for a dive, such as weather conditions, lunar phases, and wind patterns. This fragmentation of information was seen as inconvenient and time-consuming, highlighting the need for a more integrated solution.
3. **Desired Features:** One of the most commonly requested features was the integration of dive logging capabilities directly within the tide app. Divers expressed a desire for an application that could sync with their dive computers to automatically log dives, noting that this would save them time and effort. They also wanted the ability to schedule dives based on tide data, ensuring that they could plan their activities around optimal conditions. Another key feature mentioned was the inclusion of an educational section with articles, news, and events related to diving and oceanography. This would not only enhance their knowledge but also keep them updated on the latest trends and safety guidelines in the diving community.
4. **User Interface Preferences:** Interviewees emphasised the importance of a clean, intuitive, and user-friendly interface. They preferred apps that presented information in a clear and organised

manner, avoiding clutter and unnecessary details. Visual elements such as charts, maps, and graphs were highly appreciated, as they made complex data easier to understand at a glance. Users also highlighted the need for customizable views and notifications, allowing them to tailor the application to their specific needs and preferences. Consistency in design across different sections of the application was also crucial, as it helped in navigating the application smoothly without confusion.

5. **Challenges Faced:** Divers faced several challenges with the current apps. One major issue was the lack of real-time data updates, which is critical for ensuring safety during dives. Inaccurate or outdated information could lead to dangerous situations, making reliability a top priority. Another challenge was the difficulty in interpreting complex data, especially for novice divers. Apps that did not provide explanatory elements or context for the data were often found to be confusing and less useful. Additionally, divers mentioned that many apps did not support offline access, which is essential for locations with limited or no internet connectivity.

4. DISCUSSION

The development of the OceanFlow mobile application marks a significant advancement in enhancing scuba diving safety in Malaysia by providing real-time tide forecasting and an intuitive user interface. The study identified critical challenges faced by scuba divers, such as the unpredictability of tides and the associated risks of inadequate planning. By incorporating real-time tide data into a user-friendly mobile app, OceanFlow allows divers to make well-informed decisions, thereby significantly improving their safety and overall diving experience.

The user-centred design approach employed in developing OceanFlow ensured that the application is accessible and easy to use, even for individuals with limited technical skills. The positive feedback from users during the testing phase confirmed that the intuitive design and clear navigation greatly enhance the usability of the application. This accessibility is crucial, as it ensures that a broad range of users, including novice divers, can benefit from the app's safety features.

Moreover, the study highlighted the importance of real-time information in enhancing scuba diving safety. Users reported increased confidence and reduced anxiety when they had access to accurate and timely tide data, which underscores the app's potential to mitigate risks and enhance the overall diving experience. The integration of technology with practical safety measures presents a holistic approach to addressing the challenges faced by the diving community.

In conclusion, the OceanFlow application effectively addresses the key safety concerns identified in the study. It combines technological innovation with user-centred design principles to offer a practical solution for enhancing scuba diving safety. The successful implementation and positive reception of the app indicate its potential for wider application, setting a precedent for future developments in safety-oriented mobile applications.

5. CONCLUSION

The primary goal was to identify and address the gaps in existing tide forecasting tools used by scuba divers in Malaysia. The analysis of current applications revealed several significant shortcomings, including the lack of real-time data, complex interfaces, and insufficient educational resources. These issues often lead to misinformed decisions and potential safety hazards for divers.

To address these gaps, the research focused on understanding the specific needs of the scuba diving community. Interviews with diving instructors and experts provided valuable insights into the features and functionalities that would be most beneficial. The findings emphasised the demand for real-time tide data, user-friendly interfaces, and comprehensive educational resources.

Real-time data emerged as a crucial requirement. Divers stressed the need for up-to-the-minute information on tide changes, weather conditions, and other factors that could impact safety. Existing tools often relied on outdated data, which could not provide the necessary accuracy for safe dive planning. This led to the integration of real-time data updates in OceanFlow, ensuring that users always have the most current information.

User interface design was another critical focus area. The research highlighted the need for a clean, simple, and intuitive interface that could be easily navigated, even by novice users. Many existing applications were cluttered and difficult to use, especially in the demanding conditions of a diving trip. OceanFlow was designed with a minimalist and intuitive GUI, prioritising ease of use and quick access to essential features.

Educational resources were also identified as essential. The research found that divers, particularly beginners, often lacked sufficient knowledge about tide patterns, marine conditions, and safety protocols. OceanFlow includes detailed information on tide science, safety tips, and guidelines for safe diving practices, providing users with a valuable resource to enhance their understanding and preparedness.

Additionally, the study revealed the importance of customization and personalization in mobile applications. Divers preferred tools that could be tailored to their specific needs and preferences. OceanFlow offers customizable notifications, dive logs, and planning tools that allow users to set personal preferences and receive alerts tailored to their diving schedules and locations.

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